

TEACHING ENGLISH FOR MEDICAL PURPOSES

Abdukholiqova Sayramkhon Yusubjamol qizi

Fergana State University

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Annotation: The article considers the potential of the international professional development program for English language teachers of medical universities. Autonomously oriented, competency-based, contextual approaches to teaching a foreign language in a medical university are analyzed.

Keywords: advanced training program, university teachers, higher education, medical English.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the rapid development of medical science, the introduction of new technologies, as well as the multicultural and multilingual educational environment of universities, the problem of improving the qualifications of teachers of medical higher educational institutions is becoming increasingly important. With regard to teachers of a foreign language, this problem is particularly acute. The fact is that a foreign language, acting within the framework of the traditional educational paradigm as a non-core discipline, today has moved into the category of key academic subjects that ensure the success of a person's advancement in the profession. Accordingly, the methodology of teaching a foreign language is also changing radically. In fact, it is not so much about teaching a foreign language, but about teaching effective ways to use a foreign language for professional purposes. This type of training should involve diversification and multilevelness, be professionally and personally oriented, and meet current trends in medical science and education. Solving the problem of organizing a new type of learning also requires a new type of thinking that provides a creative approach to conducting classes, a willingness to create innovative learning materials based on contextual, problem-based learning methods, using an interdisciplinary approach and modern computer technologies. Of particular difficulty is the assessment of the formation of the competencies of students indicated in the federal state educational standards of higher education, the effective implementation of which seems impossible in isolation from the professional medical context.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

New approaches to the organization of teaching English for professional purposes were presented in several formats:

a) a master class on training doctors to prepare them for participation in clinical conferences in English;

- b) a master class on organizing a lesson in the form of a scientific mini-conference for graduate students;
- c) a master class on organizing a student competition of reports in a foreign language.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the above principles for the construction of advanced training programs, the main features of this course were:

- a) focus on clinical practice;
- b) emphasis on scientific activity (writing scientific articles, participation in international conferences) using a foreign language;
- c) discussion of topical psychological and pedagogical problems related to the organization of language training in medical universities (development of motivation and autonomy of teachers and students, the need to overcome the emotional burnout of teachers, educational opportunities and developing potential of the discipline "Foreign Language" in a modern context);
- d) exchange of ideas and innovative experience in the field of methods of teaching a foreign language in medical universities (development of new textbooks, application of information technologies, etc.);
- e) an informal increase in the volume of the program through the development of an information educational environment for teachers (in particular, the development and placement of materials on the personal and professional self-development of a teacher on the website of the teaching materials for linguistic disciplines).

The presented characteristics of the course reflect a new approach to building professional development programs, which, as shown by the results of the course, allows to achieve better results compared to those obtained using the traditional approach (see table).

The advanced training program included interactive lectures, several round tables and seminars, which discussed the problems of creating and developing the English-speaking environment of a modern medical university, organizing continuous training in foreign languages in medical and pharmaceutical universities and, of course, the main ways to increase its effectiveness.

Table 1

Comparison of the characteristics of the traditional and new approaches to the organization and conduct of advanced training courses for foreign language teachers of medical universities

Traditional approach	New Approach	Principles
Emphasis on conveying new	Emphasis on the involvement of students in	

information to listeners	the process of organizing courses, their active role	autonomy
Descent "from above" generalized content	Joint alignment of course content, taking into account regional needs and opportunities	
Learning from the generalized experiences of others	Using specific life experience of teachers based on its critical evaluation and exchange of experience with colleagues from other universities	
Courses as a necessity for formal professional development	Courses as an incentive for non-formal lifelong education of teachers	
The content of learning is theorized	Practice-oriented learning content reflecting modern medical science and practice	professionalization
Consideration of certain linguistic phenomena	Emphasis on interdisciplinarity	
Acquaintance with new methods that are not always relevant for the context in which teachers live and work	Building the content of training based on the real problems that teachers face in their professional activities	Problematizations
Building content based on narrowly professional topics relevant only for foreign language teachers	Building content based on interdisciplinary problems that are relevant not only within the educational environment of the university, but also in the broad context of the medical profession	
Emphasis on the quantitative arming of teachers	Emphasis on high-quality innovative self-change of teachers and their creativity	Innovation orientation

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we note that such a format of advanced training, as practice has shown, is recognized as productive not only by its participants - teachers of a foreign language, but also by foreign specialists, who note the special value for them of intercultural professional communication with various categories of subjects. the educational environment of medical universities and employees of medical institutions

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